

RECOVERY AS A RESOURCE-SAVING OPPORTUNITY

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According to reliable sources, after the first severe reality of the Covid pandemic in Europe and the stabilization of the situation in more or less, the full development of transport, resumption of flights, activation of other sectors of the economy followed by a steady rise in prices for energy carriers. A set of directives adopted by the EU at the time provided for the requirements of the new "green economy" of life and the intensive use of energy-efficient technologies, primarily to replace energy from traditional sources with renewable energy sources. Given these requirements, every country in Europe has its own strategy for achieving the goals set in this direction. , In terms of finding and introducing technical innovations. An average 10% increase in the price of gas and, consequently, a significant increase in the consumer price of electricity, together with a factor hindering the rise in prices and economic growth, provide significant motivation for the more intensive creation of renewable energy sources and the development of energy efficient technologies. Since the first steps were taken in the direction of introducing energy efficient technologies in construction in the 1970s, various types of technical means have been created, the closest types of building packaging materials have been created, construction technologies have been developed, which enable energy savings in construction and operation of buildings. There are no details when developing a strategy and selecting the technical means to achieve the desired result, globally, all the methods and technical means that are used for heating, cooling and consuming hot water by the body are even 1 watt. Allows energy savings. During the operation of any type of building, the largest amount of energy comes from heating them. Ensure the detection and proper packaging of uncontrolled energy loss sites for heating. Any type of building premise will definitely require ventilation. Traditional heating of ventilated buildings is a case of forced heat loss. In order to avoid heat loss often in domestic conditions, buildings are not ventilated, which is often the cause of the second extreme nuisance. Especially at night, the amount of oxygen in the air inside the building decreases, it is replaced by carbon dioxide, which is naturally extremely unfavorable for the health of the people there. As early as the 17th century, experiments on small animals made it clear that the cause of death was "unknown particles" emitted by the Silent and characterized by simple operating conditions. Recently, it has become important to equip buildings with intelligent engineering systems, this green construction is a special direction. Recuperators have emerged who work on the principles of sound engineering systems, such devices themselves according to the nature of the air pollution inside the building themselves choose at the time of switching on and determine the duration of the working period. This ensures the ability to effectively manage the system with maximum energy savings without human intervention. The recuperator has a special function from the combination of engineering systems required to ensure the energy efficiency of buildings, it provides a small amount of energy required for its operation, significant energy savings for heating indoor spaces and allows constant fresh air supply to indoor spaces. It should be noted that in many places, including Georgia, the Law on Energy Efficiency has been adopted. Before the law was adopted, consistent steps were taken by businesses to meet public demand. This has improved the living conditions inside the

building, saved energy, but it is unfortunate that in order to fully manage this process, there are no household recuperators on the market and therefore there is no demand, which does not make energy efficient Ability to provide full. Green construction and therefore energy efficiency is an important challenge facing the modern society, there are no minor and secondary issues in order to ensure proper results in this direction, and to achieve the result Life expectancy results. Public opinion essentially determines the timeliness of the realization of the goals and ensuring the appropriate quality in this direction. burning of candles in a closed building. The poor condition of people in spaces is caused by excessive amounts of carbon dioxide. 1982 Tesla-designed electric fan revolutionizes the ability to supply fresh air to different types of buildings. Ventilation of buildings in terms of energy efficiency must meet new requirements, at this time there should be no decrease in temperature during heating of the building, this is possible by recuperators. Air recuperation - an energy-saving feature of modern ventilation systems. This device transmits heat (energy) from the exhaust air to the incoming air. This often saves up to 40% of energy when heating a building. Recuperation is a type of green technology without which the purification of the accumulated air inside the building by the expulsion of this air produces with it the loss of energy converted into heat in the form of heat. Recuperators do not replace the boiler or other heating system, but create efficient conditions for their operation. Recuperators generate significant energy savings in living spaces, while these spaces are provided with constantly renewable fresh air, which is especially important in the conditions of the production area so that the staff working there can be provided with fresh air with heat for a reasonable period of time. This in turn provides a work environment that meets the right requirements, in such conditions labor productivity increases, production risks and production cases decrease. There are different types of recuperators working on different principles, at this time the main requirement is to choose the systems that work as much as possible.